

Inside INFRA-ART

Newsletter #01 | March 2025

Launch of the INFRA-ART newsletter

We are excited to introduce the **first issue of the INFRA-ART newsletter!** This newsletter series aims to keep you updated about the latest developments, insights, and news related to the INFRA-ART Spectral Library—a curated, FAIR data service designed as a digital support tool for heritage research specialists working with spectral data.

Our mission is to support researchers, conservators, and heritage professionals by providing open access to high-quality spectral data and tools tailored to meet their specific needs. Learn more about the mission and scope of this data service [here](#). For a more in-depth look, we encourage you to explore our original publication in the [ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage](#) as well as our latest paper featured in [Heritage](#) journal.

Moving forward... the OPEN-SciART project

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library has been awarded a two-year grant that will allow us to improve and expand the analytical capabilities of our data service. Based on the feedback received from our users, we plan to design and develop several new features and functionalities, focusing on three key areas:

- **Database expansion:** The INFRA-ART spectral database will be expanded on an ongoing basis to include new reference materials and mockup samples. New data types such as LIBS, LIF or FORS will also be integrated within the database.
- **Data analytics tools.** A range of web-based analytical toolsets will be designed and developed that will allow end-users to perform basic spectral analysis such as: peak search, peak measurement and spectral library search. This open analytical environment will provide extensive support for data analysis and interpretation while promoting data reuse.
- **FAIR educational resources.** Several digital educational resources and training materials such as video and paper tutorials focused on various topics heritage science related (e.g. applied spectroscopy, spectral data analysis and interpretation, material characterization and identification, etc.) will be developed and integrated within the INFRA-ART web page.

All of these developments will take place under the umbrella of **OPEN-SciART project**, a grant (PN-III-P1-1.1-PD-2019-1099) funded by UEFISCDI under the latest call for Young Independent Teams. Find out more about this project [here](#).

We look forward to sharing updates along the way. Stay tuned!

Advancing FAIR data practices

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library is dedicated to continually enhancing the FAIRness of its data services, with the goal of becoming a model of best practices for FAIR data management within the field of heritage science and the broader research community.

We are pleased to share that, with the support of the [FAIR-IMPACT EU Project](#), we are actively working on several FAIR-enabling capabilities to better align with EOSC guidelines, particularly in terms of data discovery, interoperability, and trustworthiness.

Under the **FAIR-IMPACT Support Cascading Grants**, we have been awarded financial support under the following actions:

- [Support offer #2](#): Creating EOSC compliant interoperability policies based on EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF).
- [Support offer #3](#): Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype.

Some of these changes, particularly those related to machine-readable metadata, have already been implemented. We are committed to continue refining our data management practices in line with FAIR principles. Additionally, as part of these efforts, we have recently updated our policy frameworks. We encourage you to review these policies and stay updated.

Latest database entries

Our most recent additions within the database include over 100 inorganic pigments sourced from [Kremer](#), ranging from cobalt-based pigments to a variety of iron oxides. These high-quality reference materials further enhance the database's ability to support accurate material identification and analysis. You can explore the full list of materials [here](#).

 Milestone alert: With this update, we've surpassed **1,000 entries** in the INFRA-ART Spectral Library—a major step toward building a comprehensive and diverse resource for the heritage science community. Stay tuned for upcoming updates as we expand the database to include new data types.

Community feedback

We value your input and welcome your feedback! Whether you are part of the cultural heritage research community or a spectral data specialist, we invite you to access, explore, and share the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. Feel free to share your thoughts, questions, and suggestions at infraart@inoe.ro. Your feedback is essential in helping us improve and guide future developments to better serve community needs.

Stay connected

Stay updated and be part of the **INFRA-ART community**:

 Subscribe to our newsletter and share it with colleagues who may find it useful.

 Follow us on [LinkedIn](#) for real-time updates, news, and project developments.

 Explore our open resources on [Zenodo](#).

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